

Machine Learning for Next-Generation Power, Performance, and Area Optimization in Semiconductor Design

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ABSTRACT

Power, Performance, and Area (PPA) optimization is a critical aspect of modern semiconductor design, driven by the demand for efficiency and compactness in electronic devices. Traditional methods rely on exhaustive, iterative processes that are both time-consuming and resource-intensive. This paper explores the application of machine learning (ML) to transform PPA optimization by leveraging advanced predictive models trained on extensive historical design data. The proposed approach achieved a remarkable power prediction accuracy of 94.6%, performance prediction accuracy of 92.8%, and area prediction accuracy of 90.5%, significantly surpassing traditional methods. Additionally, ML-driven optimization reduced design iterations by 75%, from 20 to 5, and optimization time by nearly 80%, from 48 hours to just 10 hours. Deviations from target values were minimized, with power, area, and performance deviations reduced to 1.8%, 2.3%, and 1.6%, respectively. These results demonstrate the transformative potential of ML in automating and refining PPA optimization, enabling faster, more precise, and resource-efficient design processes for future advancements in semiconductor technology.

Keywords: Power Performance Area (PPA) Optimization, Machine Learning in VLSI, Semiconductor Efficiency, Design Automation, Predictive Modeling, Resource Utilization

INTRODUCTION

The semiconductor industry has consistently driven technological advancements, with power, performance, and area (PPA) optimization emerging as critical factors in integrated circuit (IC) design. Traditional methods for PPA optimization, relying on manual, iterative approaches, are increasingly inadequate in addressing the complexities of modern semiconductor technologies. As transistor dimensions approach the sub-20 nm scale, new challenges such as increased process variability, higher leakage currents, and limited lithography resolution have necessitated innovative solutions [1]. These challenges are compounded by the need for faster design cycles and the exploration of optimal design parameters across diverse architectural configurations [2]. Machine learning (ML) has shown immense potential to address these challenges by automating complex tasks, identifying trends in historical design data, and enabling real-time optimizations [3]. Unlike conventional methods that often depend on heuristic approaches, ML techniques can handle large design spaces efficiently, offering precise predictions and configurations to optimize PPA metrics [4]. Recent advances in machine learning have introduced novel approaches to the PPA optimization process. For instance, reinforcement learning (RL) and graph convolutional networks (GCNs) have been successfully employed to optimize circuit topology and enable knowledge transfer between different technology nodes, thereby reducing design effort and time [5][6]. Moreover, Bayesian optimization and evolutionary strategies have demonstrated their ability to fine-tune transistor-level parameters and achieve significant improvements in power efficiency and area utilization [7]. As IC complexity grows, these ML-driven methodologies also facilitate the exploration of architectural parameters, such as memory banking or compiler settings, which are crucial for achieving PPA targets [8]. By integrating ML into electronic design automation (EDA) tools, designers can overcome the limitations of traditional techniques, ensuring sustainable advancements in semiconductor technologies. This paper delves into these developments, highlighting the transformative impact of ML on PPA optimization while addressing the challenges posed by emerging technologies [9][10].

The increasing demand for efficient and application-specific hardware in the era of machine learning (ML) has catalyzed a significant shift in the design of ML accelerators. These accelerators, particularly parameterizable designs tailored for field-programmable gate arrays (FPGAs) and application-specific integrated circuits (ASICs), have emerged as critical components in meeting diverse computational requirements. However, the design cycle for these accelerators, spanning architecture to silicon implementation, remains a challenging process, often requiring months of effort and the collaboration of cross-disciplinary teams [11]. Accelerators for deep neural networks (DNNs) have garnered considerable attention, with platforms like VTA, GeneSys, and Gemmini providing customizable solutions [12][13]. Conversely, accelerators for non-DNN algorithms, such as support vector machines and logistic regression, have seen comparatively limited exploration, despite their widespread applications. The TABLA framework exemplifies a notable effort in this domain, underscoring the need for robust, parameterizable solutions across diverse ML workloads [14]. Designing ML accelerators entails balancing power, performance, and area (PPA) metrics while optimizing system-level metrics such as runtime and energy consumption [15]. Traditional approaches to PPA prediction rely on computationally intensive synthesis, placement, and routing (SP&R) processes, which are time-consuming and resource-demanding [16]. Furthermore, optimizing PPA does not always guarantee improvements in runtime or energy efficiency, highlighting the complexity of design space exploration (DSE). Recent research addresses these challenges by employing physical-design-driven ML frameworks to predict PPA metrics accurately and expedite DSE processes [17]. Techniques such as Multi-Objective Tree-Structured Parzen Estimator (MOTPE)-based Bayesian optimization integrate architectural configurations with SP&R guidelines, offering a comprehensive optimization strategy for ML accelerators [18]. This approach significantly reduces the reliance on exhaustive SP&R runs, enabling faster evaluation and optimization of designs [19][20].

RELATED WORKS

Power, performance, and area (PPA) optimization is a cornerstone in semiconductor design, particularly in addressing the challenges associated with modern integrated circuits (ICs). Traditional methods for PPA optimization have relied heavily on simulation-based techniques that require substantial computational resources and extended development cycles. These methods often involve exhaustive evaluations and iterations, making them less feasible for large-scale or complex designs. Recent advancements in machine learning (ML) have paved the way for more efficient PPA optimization by enabling predictive models that reduce the reliance on computationally intensive simulations [21]. Model-based approaches have gained attention for their ability to substitute simulators with predictive models during optimization. These methods allow for rapid evaluation of design configurations and facilitate design space exploration (DSE) in a computationally efficient manner. For instance, Gaussian process regression has been used to predict SRAM yield, significantly reducing the number of evaluations required during the optimization process [22]. Similarly, adaptive surrogate modeling techniques, as explored by Yao et al., integrate on-the-fly model training with circuit simulations to enhance the accuracy of optimization outcomes [23]. However, challenges remain, particularly in ensuring the reliability and generalizability of predictive models across different stages of the IC design process [24].

The integration of reinforcement learning (RL) into transistor sizing and circuit optimization represents a significant step forward. Unlike supervised learning, RL allows continuous learning and dynamic adjustment of optimization policies, making it well-suited for the iterative nature of design processes. RL-based frameworks have demonstrated superior performance in analogy circuit optimization, leveraging graph neural networks (GNNs) to incorporate topology information and enable knowledge transfer across designs [25]. These frameworks address the limitations of earlier methods by offering scalability and adaptability, particularly in handling complex, multi-objective optimization tasks [26]. ML-based DSE methods have also been instrumental in addressing the challenges of physical design, including floor planning, placement, and routing. These stages are critical for ensuring optimal area utilization, timing performance, and routability in ICs. Techniques such as hierarchical performance estimation and Bayesian optimization have been applied to improve the efficiency of placement and routing processes [27]. Furthermore, generative adversarial networks (GANs) have been utilized for mask optimization and lithography simulation, enabling high-accuracy predictions while reducing computational costs [28]. Recent developments in high-level synthesis (HLS) and automated transistor sizing have further emphasized the role of ML in simplifying complex design workflows. For example, ML-based methods have been employed to optimize test set generation during design verification, ensuring higher accuracy and efficiency in identifying design flaws [29]. Additionally, ML techniques have been applied in functional verification, where Bayesian networks and neural networks are used to generate optimized test cases for IC validation [21].

This literature review highlights the transformative potential of machine learning in PPA optimization. By integrating ML models into various stages of semiconductor design, researchers and practitioners can overcome traditional limitations, streamline design processes, and achieve significant improvements in power efficiency, performance, and area utilization. Power, performance, and area (PPA) optimization in semiconductor design has seen extensive research leveraging both traditional and modern approaches. Analytical models like ORION [30] and

McPAT [31] have historically been used to estimate PPA at early stages, providing foundational methods for design exploration. These models, however, struggle to keep pace with the increasing complexity of modern integrated circuits (ICs). Machine learning (ML) models have emerged as a powerful alternative, offering better accuracy and scalability for PPA prediction across design stages [32]. For instance, Lin et al. introduced HL-Pow, a learning-based framework for power prediction in high-level synthesis (HLS), which effectively prunes the design space using sampling techniques [33].

Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) have shown significant potential in PPA prediction by utilizing graph-based representations of circuit topologies. Zhang et al. developed Grannite, a GNN-based tool that generates transferable power estimations for various hardware configurations, showcasing the adaptability of GNNs in design workflows [34]. Furthermore, Lu et al. employed GNNs to predict PPA during the early stages of the physical design flow, achieving better accuracy than traditional methods by leveraging structural data [35]. These studies highlight the critical role of GNNs in bridging the gap between early-stage predictions and backend physical design parameters. Design space exploration (DSE) is another area where ML models have significantly improved efficiency. AutoDNNchip, introduced by Xu et al., integrates ML predictors to optimize energy, throughput, and latency for deep neural network (DNN) accelerators, enabling faster architectural exploration [36]. Transfer learning has further enhanced DSE processes by allowing parameters from existing models to guide new design evaluations. For example, Kwon and Carloni utilized transfer learning in HLS to accelerate evaluations and achieve optimal results with fewer computational resources [37].

Approximate computing techniques have been instrumental in optimizing PPA by introducing controlled inaccuracies in computations. Functional approximation methods, such as reduced precision arithmetic and truncated operations, have been widely used to improve resource utilization in resource-constrained systems [38]. Ullah et al. proposed FPGA-based approximate multipliers optimized for specific applications, achieving substantial gains in area and energy efficiency. In memory design, ML-based approaches have transformed the prediction of energy and performance metrics for embedded memories. Neural networks have been applied to memory compiler outputs to predict PPA with high accuracy, enabling faster and more reliable design iterations [6]. Transfer learning has been particularly effective in reducing the retraining overhead for different memory configurations, further streamlining the design process. Despite these advancements, integrating ML across all stages of semiconductor design remains a challenge. Existing frameworks like HL-Pow [4] and AutoDNNchip [7] have laid the groundwork for comprehensive solutions by combining early-stage predictions with backend design parameters. Such integrated approaches have the potential to revolutionize PPA optimization, offering accurate, scalable, and efficient methodologies for next-generation semiconductor designs.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology outlines the approach for implementing machine learning (ML) models to optimize Power, Performance, and Area (PPA) in semiconductor design. This section describes the data preparation, model training, feature engineering, evaluation metrics, and optimization strategy, ensuring reproducibility and accuracy. The dataset utilized for this study includes historical semiconductor design configurations and their corresponding PPA metrics. These data points are derived from previous design cycles and include parameters such as transistor counts, clock frequencies, supply voltages, and layout dimensions. The following steps were employed for data preprocessing:

- Outliers and incomplete entries were removed to ensure data consistency.
- Features were scaled to a uniform range, ensuring that variables with large magnitudes do not dominate the learning process. The min-max normalization formula was used:

$$x' = \frac{x - \min(x)}{\max(x) - \min(x)}$$

- Categorical variables such as design types or fabrication technologies were encoded using one-hot encoding.

To enhance model performance, feature engineering was applied to extract meaningful patterns. Derived features include:

- Power Efficiency Ratios:

$$\text{Efficiency} = \frac{\text{Output power}}{\text{Total power consumption}}$$

- Area Utilization Metrics:

$$Utilization = \frac{Active\ Component\ Area}{Total\ Chip\ Area}$$

- Performance Indices:

$$Performance\ Index = Clock\ Speed \times Number\ of\ Processing\ Units$$

Correlation analysis was performed to identify and retain only the most impactful features for PPA prediction. Multiple ML algorithms were evaluated, including Random Forest (RF), Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM), and Neural Networks (NN). The primary focus was to develop a model that accurately predicts PPA metrics and identifies optimal configurations.

- Model Architecture: A neural network with the following structure was implemented:
 - Input Layer: Feature vector of size n , representing design parameters.
 - Hidden Layers: Three fully connected layers with ReLU activation.
 - Output Layer: Three nodes representing predicted power, performance, and area values.

The loss function used for optimization was the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE):

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_i - \hat{y}_i}{y_i} \right| \times 100$$

The dataset was split into training (70%), validation (15%), and testing (15%) subsets. A stratified sampling technique ensured representation of all design configurations. Key aspects of training include:

- Optimization Algorithm: Adam optimizer was used with a learning rate of 0.001.
- Batch Size: 64 samples per batch to balance computational efficiency and model generalization.
- Early Stopping: Validation loss was monitored to prevent overfitting.

The performance of the ML models was evaluated using standard metrics such as Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and R-squared (R^2) for each PPA metric:

- RMSE:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - y^i)^2}$$

- R^2 :

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

To refine PPA outcomes, the trained model was coupled with an optimization algorithm based on Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO). PSO was used to explore the design space efficiently by minimizing the weighted sum of power, performance, and area deviations:

Objective Function

$$\begin{aligned} &= w_1(\text{Predicted Power} - \text{Target Power})^2 \\ &+ w_2(\text{Predicted Performance} - \text{Target Performance})^2 \\ &+ w_3(\text{Predicted Area} - \text{Target Area})^2 \end{aligned}$$

Weights (w_1 , w_2 , w_3) were adjusted based on design priorities. The proposed ML model was integrated into the Electronic Design Automation (EDA) workflow. Predictions were fed into downstream tools for layout synthesis, enabling iterative refinement of designs with reduced manual intervention. This methodology demonstrates a

systematic application of ML for PPA optimization, ensuring improved semiconductor design efficiency and reduced design cycle time.

Architecture

Figure 1: Machine Learning Architecture for Power, Performance, and Area (PPA) Optimization in Semiconductor Design

The architecture flowchart represents the systematic integration of machine learning (ML) techniques into the semiconductor design process to optimize Power, Performance, and Area (PPA). The process begins with data collection and preprocessing, where historical semiconductor design data, including power consumption, clock frequencies, transistor counts, and layout details, are gathered. These datasets undergo noise reduction, normalization, and feature encoding to prepare them for ML model training. The next stage involves feature engineering, where critical design parameters are extracted and new features are derived, such as power efficiency ratios, area utilization metrics, and performance indices. This step ensures that the most relevant features are provided to the ML model to improve predictive accuracy.

The core of the architecture lies in the machine learning model training phase. Various algorithms, such as Random Forests, Gradient Boosting, and Neural Networks, are tested, with a focus on developing a neural network model for multi-objective prediction of power, performance, and area metrics. The model's input layer receives the feature vector, which passes through hidden layers with non-linear activation functions to capture complex relationships, and outputs predicted PPA values. Once trained, the model integrates with an optimization engine, employing techniques like Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) to fine-tune design configurations. The optimization process aligns predicted values with design goals, balancing trade-offs between power, performance, and area based on specific weights assigned to each metric. Finally, the architecture includes workflow integration, where ML predictions feed into Electronic Design Automation (EDA) tools. These tools perform layout synthesis and iterative refinement, enabling automated adjustments to semiconductor designs. This seamless integration reduces manual interventions, accelerates the design cycle, and enhances overall efficiency. This architecture ensures a robust and efficient pipeline for leveraging ML to address the challenges of PPA optimization in modern semiconductor design.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained from the machine learning-driven Power, Performance, and Area (PPA) optimization demonstrate the transformative potential of this approach in modern semiconductor design. Key metrics, including model accuracy, optimization efficiency, and comparative performance against traditional methods, have been analyzed and presented in tabular format. The discussion highlights the effectiveness of machine learning techniques in identifying optimal design configurations and their implications for future advancements in electronic device manufacturing.

Figure 2: Performance Metrics of the Machine Learning Model

Figure 2 illustrates the performance accuracy of three machine learning models—Random Forest (RF), Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM), and Neural Network (NN)—in predicting Power, Performance, and Area (PPA) metrics. These results correspond directly to Table 1, which quantifies the accuracy percentages for each model across the three prediction tasks. From the data, it is evident that the Neural Network consistently outperforms both RF and GBM across all metrics. Specifically, the Neural Network achieves a power prediction accuracy of 94.6%, a performance prediction accuracy of 92.8%, and an area prediction accuracy of 90.5%. These values indicate a significant improvement over RF, which achieves respective accuracies of 88.5%, 86.2%, and 85.4%, and over GBM, with accuracies of 91.3%, 89.7%, and 87.9%. The trends observed in the figure show a descending pattern for all three models as the complexity of the prediction task increases from power to area. The Neural Network’s ability to retain higher accuracy across all three metrics highlights its capacity to model complex non-linear relationships inherent in the data. Gradient Boosting Machine performs moderately well but shows a noticeable gap compared to the Neural Network, while Random Forest, although still effective, has the lowest accuracy across all metrics.

Table 1: Performance Metrics of the Machine Learning Model

Metric	Power Prediction Accuracy (%)	Performance Prediction Accuracy (%)	Area Prediction Accuracy (%)
Random Forest	88.5	86.2	85.4
Gradient Boosting Machine	91.3	89.7	87.9
Neural Network	94.6	92.8	90.5

This table 1 shows the predictive accuracy of the ML models used for PPA optimization. The neural network demonstrated superior accuracy across all metrics compared to Random Forest and Gradient Boosting Machine models. The superior performance of the Neural Network can be attributed to its deeper architecture, which allows it to capture intricate patterns and relationships in the semiconductor design dataset. In contrast, the ensemble-based methods, RF and GBM, face limitations in representing the multi-dimensional dependencies between design parameters and PPA outcomes. These results underscore the importance of selecting advanced machine learning models, such as Neural Networks, for tasks requiring high precision in semiconductor design optimization. The ability of the Neural Network to achieve accuracies exceeding 90% across all metrics demonstrates its potential as a robust tool for driving efficiency and precision in Power, Performance, and Area optimization.

Figure 3 provides a graphical representation of the optimization outcomes for three design configurations, which are summarized in Table 2. The graphs in the figure highlight the predicted values versus the target values for power, area, and performance metrics, as well as the prediction error percentages for each configuration. For power prediction, shown in subfigure (a), the predicted power values closely match the target power values for all three configurations. Configuration 1 has a target power of 15 W and a predicted value of 14.8 W, while Configuration 2 and Configuration 3 show similarly small deviations with predicted values of 19.7 W and 24.5 W, respectively.

These results demonstrate a minimal error margin, as further emphasized in subfigure (d), where the power prediction error remains below 2% for all configurations. For area prediction, illustrated in subfigure (b), the predicted values align closely with the target values, reflecting a similar trend of high accuracy. For Configuration 1, the predicted area is 118 mm² compared to the target of 120 mm², while Configurations 2 and 3 show equally small deviations of 2 mm² and 1 mm², respectively. Subfigure (e) highlights the area prediction error, which decreases progressively from Configuration 1 to Configuration 3, with Configurations 2 and 3 achieving prediction errors below 1.5%.

Figure 3: Optimization Outcomes for Design Configurations in PPA Prediction

Regarding performance prediction, subfigure (c) depicts the predicted values for all configurations closely matching their respective targets. Configuration 1 has a target performance of 2.5 GHz and a predicted value of 2.52 GHz, while Configurations 2 and 3 show deviations of only 0.02 GHz and 0.01 GHz, respectively. Subfigure (f) demonstrates that the performance prediction error remains below 1% for all configurations, showcasing the model's exceptional accuracy in performance prediction.

Table 2: Optimization Outcomes for Design Configurations

Configuration ID	Target Power (W)	Predicted Power (W)	Target Area (mm ²)	Predicted Area (mm ²)	Target Performance (GHz)	Predicted Performance (GHz)
Config-1	15	14.8	120	118	2.5	2.52
Config-2	20	19.7	150	148	3.0	3.02
Config-3	25	24.5	180	179	3.5	3.49

The optimization outcomes reveal the ability of the ML model to closely align predicted values with target PPA objectives. The minimal deviation across power, area, and performance metrics confirms the model's precision. Overall, these results validate the effectiveness of the machine learning model in predicting PPA metrics with high precision across all three configurations. The minimal deviations between target and predicted values, along with the low error percentages, highlight the reliability of the optimization process. These findings underscore the suitability of the ML-driven approach for streamlining PPA optimization in semiconductor design, enabling accurate predictions that align closely with design objectives while significantly reducing manual effort and design iteration time.

Figure 4: Comparison of ML-Driven Optimization and Traditional Iterative Design Methods

The figure illustrates the comparative analysis between ML-driven optimization and traditional iterative design methodologies, as presented in Table 3. It highlights key performance metrics, including design iterations, total optimization time, and deviations in power, area, and performance predictions. In subfigure (a), the significant reduction in design iterations achieved through ML-driven optimization is evident. Traditional iterative methods require 20 iterations, while the ML-driven approach reduces this to just 5 iterations, representing a 75% decrease. This reduction underscores the efficiency of machine learning models in quickly converging toward optimal design configurations without requiring extensive manual adjustments. Subfigure (b) showcases the total optimization time required by each methodology. The traditional method demands 48 hours for optimization, whereas the ML-driven approach completes the task in only 10 hours, achieving a reduction of nearly 80%. This improvement is critical in accelerating the semiconductor design cycle, allowing faster time-to-market for new products.

The accuracy of predictions is further analyzed in subfigures (c) and (d). Subfigure (c) focuses on power deviation, where the traditional method shows a deviation of 6.5%, while the ML-driven approach significantly reduces this to 1.8%. Similarly, subfigure (d) highlights deviations in area and performance predictions. For area deviation, the traditional method records 8.2%, whereas the ML-driven approach achieves a reduced deviation of 2.3%. Performance deviation follows a similar trend, with the traditional method recording 7.3%, while ML-driven optimization limits it to 1.6%. These results collectively demonstrate the superior accuracy and efficiency of ML-driven optimization compared to traditional iterative methods. The substantial reduction in iterations and optimization time highlights the practicality of integrating machine learning models into semiconductor design workflows. Furthermore, the reduced deviations across all metrics indicate the reliability of the ML-driven

approach in meeting PPA targets with higher precision. The findings underline the transformative impact of machine learning in addressing the inefficiencies of traditional design methods. By streamlining optimization processes and improving prediction accuracy, ML-driven optimization not only enhances the performance of semiconductor designs but also reduces the overall resource consumption and time requirements, paving the way for more efficient and sustainable design practices. Table 3 compares the ML-driven approach with traditional iterative design methods. The ML model significantly reduces the number of design iterations and optimization time while achieving lower deviations across all PPA metrics.

Table 3: Comparison of ML-Driven Optimization with Traditional Methods

Methodology	Design Iterations	Total Optimization Time (Hours)	Power Deviation (%)	Area Deviation (%)	Performance Deviation (%)
Traditional Iterative Design	20	48	6.5	8.2	7.3
ML-Driven Optimization	5	10	1.8	2.3	1.6

The results of this study demonstrate the effectiveness and transformative potential of machine learning (ML) in optimizing Power, Performance, and Area (PPA) in semiconductor design. The findings highlight critical improvements in prediction accuracy, optimization efficiency, and resource utilization when compared to traditional iterative design methods. The performance metrics from the machine learning models underline the superiority of neural networks in predicting PPA values with high precision. With prediction accuracies exceeding 90% for power, performance, and area metrics, the neural network consistently outperformed other models such as Random Forest and Gradient Boosting Machines. This superior performance is attributed to the neural network's ability to capture complex non-linear relationships in the data, making it particularly suitable for tasks requiring intricate pattern recognition and multi-objective optimization.

The optimization outcomes for various design configurations further validate the accuracy and robustness of the ML-driven approach. Across all configurations, the predicted values for power, area, and performance closely aligned with their respective target values, achieving deviations of less than 2% for power and performance metrics, and less than 1.5% for area metrics. This level of precision ensures that design objectives are met with minimal error, significantly enhancing the reliability of the design process. A comparative analysis between ML-driven optimization and traditional iterative methods underscores the substantial advantages of integrating machine learning into the design workflow. The ML-driven approach reduced design iterations by 75% and optimization time by nearly 80%, demonstrating its capability to streamline the design process and accelerate time-to-market for semiconductor products. Furthermore, deviations in power, area, and performance metrics were reduced by over 70% in ML-driven optimization, showcasing its accuracy in meeting design requirements with fewer resources and reduced manual intervention.

The reduced design iterations and optimization time not only improve efficiency but also lower computational costs and resource consumption, making the ML-driven approach highly scalable for modern semiconductor design challenges. Additionally, the ability of the machine learning model to quickly adapt to varying design parameters and constraints highlights its flexibility and applicability across different design scenarios. These results collectively emphasize the critical role of machine learning in revolutionizing PPA optimization for semiconductor design. The ML-driven approach addresses the limitations of traditional methods, such as prolonged iteration cycles and high resource demands, by providing a fast, accurate, and automated solution. This advancement not only enhances the design process but also aligns with the industry's growing demands for efficient, compact, and high-performance electronic devices. In this study demonstrates that machine learning offers a powerful and practical alternative to traditional methods, driving significant improvements in efficiency and precision. By leveraging the capabilities of advanced ML models, future semiconductor designs can achieve optimized PPA outcomes while reducing design complexity and cost, paving the way for further innovation in electronic device manufacturing.

CONCLUSION

This research demonstrates the effectiveness of integrating machine learning (ML) techniques into the Power, Performance, and Area (PPA) optimization process for semiconductor design. The results highlight significant improvements in both prediction accuracy and optimization efficiency, validating the transformative potential of ML-driven approaches. The neural network model achieved exceptional predictive accuracy, with power prediction at 94.6%, performance prediction at 92.8%, and area prediction at 90.5%. These results establish neural networks as highly reliable tools for accurately predicting design outcomes in semiconductor workflows. Moreover, the optimization results show minimal deviations from target values, with power deviation reduced to 1.8%, area deviation to 2.3%, and performance deviation to 1.6%. These low error margins reflect the precision and robustness

of the ML-driven approach. When compared to traditional iterative design methods, ML-driven optimization reduced design iterations by 75%, from 20 iterations to 5, and decreased total optimization time by nearly 80%, from 48 hours to just 10 hours. These improvements significantly streamline the design process, demonstrating the efficiency of machine learning in meeting tight development timelines while maintaining high accuracy. The findings underscore the practical benefits of ML-driven optimization, including enhanced predictive capabilities, reduced design complexity, and significant time and resource savings. This approach addresses the limitations of traditional methods, enabling semiconductor designers to achieve high performance, power efficiency, and compact area configurations in less time and with greater reliability. In conclusion, the integration of machine learning into PPA optimization provides a powerful and efficient framework for next-generation semiconductor design. The demonstrated accuracy and efficiency of ML-driven methods make them indispensable tools for addressing the increasing demands of modern electronic devices. Future research should explore the scalability of these methods across more complex design scenarios and further enhance model interpretability to foster wider adoption in the semiconductor industry.

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